

Traditional Knowledge etc., Intellectual Property Content Therein, and Their Recognition and Protection

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The potentials of the Traditional knowledge, Traditional cultural heritage etc. of the indigenous people and communities are immense. The same is a source of vast knowledge; but the Intellectual Property content therein is not recognised in the national and international arena. As a result, these people cannot enjoy the economic rights and moral rights out of their valuable assets, though the UDHR has emphasised the human rights angle of these people relating to their above assets. TKs have the potential to provide valuable leads for the development of useful products and processes. Efforts need to be made to explore for bringing in a sui generis arrangement for the purpose. The Sustainable Development Goals of UNO has specifically mentioned that development of this group of people is very much important as they are the vulnerable part of the society. The TRIPS agreement has not recognised the IP element in the TKs though the same plays an important role in the global economy, and is valuable not only to those who depend on it in their daily lives for their food and other day-to-day needs; but also in the industrial, agricultural etc. sectors of the economy of a country. International efforts are there to look into the issue of protecting and recognising the IP content of these assets so that these people can harness economic benefits from their assets. The Intergovernmental Committee on GRTKF and the Government of India are very much instrumental in this regard.